

IS THE NUMBER OF CITATIONS OF AN ARTICLE THE BEST WAY TO DETERMINE ITS SCIENTIFIC QUALITY

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Abstract

The exponential growth of the Internet and the availability of online and open-access journals have led to new challenges in science. In such a situation, a significant problem for research scientists is keeping up with published research due to the large number of research results, which results in only part of the literature being read and subsequently cited. Quite significant in terms of citations is the “Matthew effect,” according to which a paper with many citations will collect even more citations than, for example, a comparable similar paper with fewer or no citations (a self-propagation cycle; Ioannidis), or the “citation snowball,” because “everyone cites it” (Martin Kaon). Inexperienced and unestablished authors, seeing certain cited papers in the introductions of well-known authors, are led to think that they should cite the same papers in their introductions as some kind of unwritten convention in the field (even if they are not directly relevant).

A lack of citations does not necessarily mean that a work is of lower quality. The number of citations can be influenced by a number of factors, including the age of the article (even Nobel Prize-winning papers start with zero citations), disciplinary norms, access, co-authorship by dozens of experts in a single paper, networking and citation-trading schemes (clientelism, cronyism, non-founded colleague solidarity), self-citations, and even citations forced by reviewers.

To make citation counting more meaningful (or perhaps to hide the shortcomings of the system), modern managers and research organizations have chosen to use words such as “research quality” and “impact” to disguise the fact that it is merely the “total number of citations,” thus covertly giving these words a new, different definition when the consumer assumes the older, traditional meaning.

The numerous challenges related to this topic are, in this paper, analyzed through the prism of the undeniable facts of the rapid commercialization and instrumentalization of science, as the most subtle weapon in achieving long-term geopolitical and geo-economic interests of the most powerful actors on the global stage. The preferred epistemological matrix through which such goals are achieved is naïve positivist empiricism, which converges toward the methodological paradigm of the inductive illusion, characterized by an overemphasized use of quantitative methods.

Now, quality assessment is democratized because experts can “vote” on the quality of a paper by citing it. Previously, quality was assessed subjectively by individual scientists. Is it more optimal for the assessment of the scientific quality of a paper to remain a transparent collegial exercise of “all experts” (taking into account the weaknesses of representative-liberal democracy), or could a qualitatively new transparent procedure with objectified criteria for the presence of the immanent scientific functions and goals in a

paper – carried out by a multi-member commission of the most competent and impartial scientists, in which any possible conflict of interest or influence would be excluded – be considered more optimal instead? The answer to this extremely important research question for the development of science is given in this paper.

Key words: number of citations, scientific quality of an article

INTRODUCTION

It is considered that from the time Henry Oldenburg created the *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London* in the seventeenth century, scientists have endeavored to share the results of their research efforts with a wider audience by publishing in scientific journals (Guédon J-C, 2001). Since that time, many new journals have been founded, giving authors many options for publishing. This has been particularly significant in recent years due to the growth of the Internet and the availability of online and open-access journals (Larivière V., Gingras Y., Archambault É., 2009; Armato S., Baldock C., Orton C.G., 2015).

With such growth have come challenges. A significant issue for active research scientists is keeping up to date with published research due to the large body of research outputs, resulting in only a fraction of the literature being read and subsequently cited (Meho L.I., 2007). Due to many published papers going unnoticed or unread, many articles either never get cited or are only self-cited by their authors. When a paper is published, it has no immediate impact. However, many would contend that the number of times a paper is subsequently cited is a good indicator of its impact and therefore of the quality of the research (Biagioli M., Lippman A., 2020).

First of all, we will present the sublimated thesis of those authors who claim that the number of citations is a good way to determine the quality of certain research, as well as the counterarguments against them. So, how can one determine the quality of a quantum of research? A quantum in this case is an article published in a peer-reviewed scientific journal, supported by a constituted national or international society of scientists sharing a common interest in a particular field of endeavor.

Being published in a journal means that the manuscript has navigated the obstacle course of peer review and has been adjudged to be sound, novel, and of publishable quality by some members of the academic community. The historical gold standard for assessing published articles has been: be an expert in the field, read a hard copy, and assess it in the light of one's own expertise. Unfortunately, this method was available only to experts with access to the journal. Fortunately, science advances.

Electronic publication has provided novel, measurable ways to access research. This ability to measure is important. William Thomson stated: "When you can measure what you are speaking about, and express it in numbers, you know something about it; when you cannot express it in numbers, your knowledge is of a meagre and unsatisfactory kind" (Lord Kelvin, 1883). Citation metrics mean that the assessment of research quality has left behind the dark ages of meagre and unsatisfactory knowledge. By expressing quality as a number, we know that we know something about it.

What metrics are available to us? The "number of reads" is a measure of scientific interest. However, "number of downloads" is a better metric as it implies that the interest is sufficiently deep to require a sustained effort to understand the published work. The NoD is directly proportional to the quality of the article. Contrarily, it may be argued that some

scientists download poor-quality articles to make a point, but people soon tire of reading nonsense, and return to quality. In fact, the NoD may even underestimate interest, as PDF copies electronically sent to colleagues save them from downloading it anew.

A still better metric is the number of citations (NoC) made to published work. Scientists who cite an article are a subset of those who download it. Citing scientists have read the article, found it relevant and useful, and wish to associate their own work with it. Such scientists are themselves researchers who have the expertise to recognize important work. They are part of the community of cognoscenti, and their number can be counted. Now we can say that five scientists have noticed this work, or that fifty-five scientists approve of it. We have an improved gold standard.

The record of quality is permanent. The number of citations remains on record and increases over time, making the importance of the work more apparent. Hence, the number of citations is flexible and responsive to changes in knowledge. It is unlikely that modern-day scientists will overlook the work or that it will be forgotten, as has happened in the past. The metrification of quality allows for better metrics to be introduced. For example, the Relative Citation Ratio measures quality at the article level (Hutchins B.I., Yuan X. et al., 2016; Purkayastha A., Palmaro E. et al., 2019). This metric addresses the widely acknowledged limitations of raw citation counts by accounting for field of study and time of publication, using expected citation rates derived from all citations to contributions of the same type published in the same year in the same ISI journal.

Just as cobalt machines have been relegated to the basement by modern linear accelerators, X-ray film has been supplanted by digital radiography, CT scanning has become helical, and few medical physicists now know what a typewriter is, so too has the modern assessment of quality improved and supplanted historical methods. **The assessment of quality has been democratized because scientists can now “vote” on the quality of a manuscript by citing it.** Previously, quality was assessed subjectively by individual scientists reading the article. Now quality assessment is a transparent collegial exercise based on consensus among expert researchers, rather than the whim of individual scientists.

However, the above-mentioned thesis has opposing arguments.

The second meaningful and sublimated thesis denies the claim that the number of citations is the optimal way to determine the quality of certain research. Namely, the modern concept of citation indexing in research was introduced by Eugene Garfield in 1955, based on the earlier legal citation database *Shepard's Citations*, which dates back to 1873 (Garfield E., 1955). The purpose of a legal citation database is to ensure that precedents set in legal cases can be easily found and used in later court decisions. Garfield argued that a similar citation database for academic research could serve as a useful tool for locating earlier research so that it can be built upon, rather than rediscovered, and so that criticisms of earlier research are more readily available to inform future directions. In Garfield's paper, the term *Impact Factor* was introduced in relation to the number of citations an article or journal receives.

Garfield's argument – that the number of times a particular item, discovery, or methodology is used to build later research reflects its influence – holds true; however, simply counting all citations also includes instances in which an item has been criticized. **For example, Radicchi showed that papers criticized via comments are cited more frequently than non-commented papers and are more likely to be among the most cited within a journal** (Radicchi F., 2012). Although a paper that is commented on and

criticized is not necessarily of low quality – and criticism itself is often debunked by author responses –there are certainly cases in which criticism is valid, yet the act of criticizing a paper still contributes to its “impact” and thus its perceived “quality” through citation counts.

It has recently been shown that 74% of citations occur in the Introduction and Discussion sections of papers (Gerlach M., P-C et al., 2019). A proper introduction situates the present research within the context of recent progress and existing gaps in knowledge, while a good discussion contextualizes the results. However, when a paper is cited in an introduction or discussion, one must consider whether it genuinely informs the present research or merely follows convention. Inexperienced authors, in particular, may feel compelled to include lengthy introductions citing numerous articles simply to emulate the format of other papers. If such cited works do not directly contribute to the presented research, they effectively state only that “others have worked on something similar, but not quite the same.” Truly influential papers – those introducing new processes, procedures, or discoveries – are more likely to be cited in the methodology section, where they directly influence future work. This raises the question of whether citation metrics should be based on all citations or only the 26% that do not occur in introductions or discussions.

These arguments can be extended further through consideration of the Matthew effect (Baldock C., Schreiner L.J., Orton C., 2017), which is eloquently illustrated by Ioannidis (Ioannidis J.P.A., 2018). **In short, the Matthew effect refers to the tendency for already well-cited papers to attract even more citations than comparable papers with fewer or no citations, creating a self-propagating cycle.** Ioannidis discusses this phenomenon in relation to oversimplified research tools, but the concept can be generalized to **other contexts such as inexperienced authors who may observe frequently cited papers in introductions and assume they should cite the same works in their own papers, even when not directly relevant, thereby perpetuating the citation cycle.**

Certainly, a lack of citations does not imply that a piece of work is of lower quality. **Citation counts are influenced by numerous factors** (Tahamtan I., Afshar A.S., Ahamdzadeh K., 2016), **including the age of the article, disciplinary norms, access** (De Groote S.L., 2008), **large co-authorship teams, networking and citation-trading schemes, self-citation** (Ioannidis J.P.A., Baas J. et al., 2019), **and even reviewer-coerced citations** (Wren J.D., Valencia A., Kelso J., 2019).

Implicit in the claim that “citations are a good way to determine research quality” is the assumption that citations are appropriate and properly placed. Spurious citations can undermine reader confidence and lead to dismissal of an article. A paper cited in an introduction for reporting a novel result is not inherently less worthy of citation than one cited in a methods section for technical parameters. **However, citation snowballing – where papers are cited simply because “everyone cites them” – is recognized and dismissed by discerning researchers.**

Peer criticism is an essential mechanism for improving research quality, as it exposes shortcomings that can be avoided in future work. While a critical citation does not necessarily signal high quality, it contributes to the advancement of knowledge. Thus, lack of citation does not imply lack of quality (Armato S., Baldock C., Orton C.G., 2015). Taking into consideration all of the above mentioned, the premise of citation counting is that the total number of citations received is not the sole indicator of the quality or impact of a piece of research, regardless of whether the citation is positive, negative, or merely

included to fill in the introduction and bibliography. Citation counting is easy to measure, originating from the time when bibliometrics began, when tables of contents and bibliographies were the easiest data to analyse with the tools available at the time. To make citation counting appear more meaningful (or perhaps to hide the flaws of the system), contemporary research managers and organisations have chosen to use terms like “research quality” and “impact” to disguise the fact that it is merely a “total citation count”, thereby surreptitiously assigning new meaning to these terms while the reader assumes their older, traditional meaning. This is classic case of cognitive bias (imagine, for example, if “quality” were suddenly redefined to mean “word count”, then very long articles would be considered more important than concise ones, and important works in currently high-ranking journals with strict word limits – say, 1,500 words – would suffer).

RESEARCH, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, I believe that, in order to clarify the research question, it is necessary to examine the contemporary trend of the inductivist illusion and quantophobia in “scientific” papers with an “impact factor,” viewed through the prism of the immanent scientific functions and objectives, as well as the opposing tendency to these scientific functions and objectives, namely naïve empiricist positivism.

The measurability, comparability, and verifiability of empirical data obtained through scientifically based empirical research, which can be repeated and confirmed by other researchers, as significant parameters of modern methodology, have yielded great results in many spheres of social life. Otherwise, completely free logics (contemplations) on topics that can be measured and verified, no matter how clever they may seem, will float outside the reality available to humans if they are not verified by experience. For these reasons, **positivist empiricism and realism**, no matter how criticized they are (Kenneth N. Waltz, 2008), have a real dimension in science, but also a need for further critical development. In this regard, although especially **naïve positivist empiricism and naïve realism** are very convincingly and reasonably criticized by a few deeply conscious scientists in the world today (Alan Brayman, 2015), they not only show an unprecedented tenacity in science, but have become dogmatically prescribed patterns for scientific research. Namely, today it is almost impermissible for a certain topic to be the subject of scientific research if it cannot be measured and empirically verified. In this way, many important topics for humans, which are intangible and empirically immeasurable, remain outside the scope of scientific research, although only science can irreplaceably contribute to the greatest possible understanding of paradoxical reality and to proposing scientific approaches for its adaptation (improvement) to human needs (Scott Peck, 1995).

Namely, among most social scientists today, there is no clear determinant for the possibility of assessing the different degrees of scientific (and thus social) validity between different scientific theories and concepts which relate to a similar topic, for the same space and time, which advocate the same value goals, and whose different approaches, methods, means, and solutions – within the framework of commonly accepted moral norms and value convictions – should be the subject of scientific assessment. For certain most important value priorities in contemporary societies, there is a value consensus, as opposed to legitimate value pluralism and relativism. Thus, even in exemplary, anthological collections of knowledge (textbooks, monographs, scholarly works, etc.), most social scientists refrain from clearly articulating which ontological and epistemological currents predominantly inform their positions on the role of theory vis-à-vis research. Consequently, they do not hold a clearly articulated personal position on the question of

whether objective scientific evaluation and comparison of the scientific value of scholarly works, concepts, and theories is, for them, possible and necessary. Moreover, objective scientific evaluation and comparison should extend even between so-called “ordinary” scientific works and those that, under questionable “scientific” criteria and circumstances – considered as a general, trend-driven phenomenon rather than merely isolated incidents – are granted the status of original (source) scientific contributions with a so-called “impact factor,” published in global, highly prestigious international scientific journals indexed in the Scopus or Web of Science databases.

In this way, social scientists today, in the best cases consciously, but in most cases unconsciously, unclearly, and contradictorily, very indicatively incline toward constructionism or postmodernism in science, replacing the basic rationalist principle – objectivity – with the **subjectivist and relativistic motto of postmodernism: truth is accidental and debatable; there is no difference between bad and good art or bad and good science; all knowledge is equally valid** (Jan Art Scholte, 2008). This represents a conscious or unconscious convergence toward an unfounded relativization of scientific truth, for which some of them declaratively and quite contradictorily advocate. Otherwise, if the authors’ position is conscious, they lack a clearly formulated explanation of the arguments underlying that position. Of course, no theory or scientific conception can be absolutely true, but within their relative scientific truthfulness it can and should be determined which of the various concepts (in the above-mentioned sense) has a relatively greater degree of scientific truthfulness or validity. However, it must be said that among the most conscious social scientists today, there is a clearly expressed orientation toward the basic postulates of certain epistemological directions, with consciously accepted admixtures from other epistemologies. Thus, among rationalists there is a tendency toward reflexive rationalism (Gorz, 1988; Anthony Giddens; Ulrich Beck), while some postmodernists in science do not completely abandon rationalist postulates (Jan Art Scholte, 2008).

Contrary to the majority of social scientists – some of whom consciously, but most of whom unconsciously, given their unclear, contradictory, and unfounded relativistic understandings of determining the scientific value of certain scientific theories and concepts, incline toward ontological directions opposite to objectivism and toward non-rationalist epistemologies – although the majority of “scientists” today declaratively and contradictorily advocate rationalist epistemology in science (Mojanoski, T. C., 2015), **the author of this paper clearly defines his ontological orientation toward objectivism and his epistemological orientation toward reflective rationalism and critical empiricism, positivism, and realism.**

Rationalist epistemology, based on the principles of secularism, anthropocentrism, scientism, and instrumentalism, still represents the dominant epistemological current in conventional science worldwide, despite tendencies toward the infiltration of non-rationalist epistemologies, such as postmodernism in sociology and criminology. Otherwise, non-rationalistic epistemologies (interpretivism, constructionism, postmodernism, theological conceptions, various spiritual teachings based on relativist and ultra-skeptical philosophical conceptions, and the like) have a deep basis for their existence in philosophy, art, and religion. However, due to the lack of principles of truth, objectivity, verifiability, and comparability of theoretical hypotheses with indisputable empirical facts, non-rationalistic epistemologies cannot, at this stage of civilizational development and level of social consciousness, be practically usable in conventional science. Thus, for example, they are not practically applicable to social issues when opposing parties share

the same goal – that is, when there are no major value divergences or moral disagreements – but differ only in their approaches to finding the most optimal solutions for achieving common goal priorities within the framework of morally permissible and mutually acceptable values.

I assert this because rationalist epistemology, *inter alia*, grounds itself in the rational confrontation of arguments based on logical principles which, in the vast majority of cases, pertain to issues rooted in human empirical reality. As such, these arguments can be substantiated and verified by undisputed and adequate facts drawn from reality. In this sense, with regard to social issues for which there are no moral disagreements or differences in value convictions among opposing scientific theories or concepts (the goal being the same), it becomes possible – if one so wishes – to discern which theory (concept, thesis) currently provides the most adequate answer to the deeper layers of the endless causal interconnections of particular phenomena, processes, and relations, as well as to their externally manifesting reflections in the specific subject of research. Likewise, within this context, an opportunity emerges to identify which scientific concept proposes more optimal solutions for the substantial improvement or overcoming of certain significant social problems within a given socio-historical constellation of forces and relations in a particular society.

Theories do not determine facts, but for each group of facts, different theoretical concepts can provide different explanations. Among other factors, this issue is also related to the value dimension that the authors of various theories, depending on their philosophical or ideological-political matrix, can add to the facts. This problem is particularly pronounced in the social sciences, which, due to the nature of their subject of research, cannot be completely de-ideologized. **Hence, the author's position is that for issues for which there are diametrically opposed value approaches and consequently major moral disagreements, rationalist epistemology and its immanent rational confrontation of arguments is not applicable (has no effect).**

My personal opinion is that it is necessary to respect scientific ethics and professional standards in science so that the scientist remains as value-neutral as possible, that is, scientifically objective, taking into account that a completely (ideally) value-neutral person – and thus a scientist – does not exist (except in possibly rare examples). **Otherwise, in reality, without theories, facts exist in their “pure” substrate, free from value dimensions.** Dialectical immanence implies that even the best current theories do not explain facts once and for all. **Hence arises the well-known fact, confirmed in the history of science, that currently best theories can be replaced by even better theories if they manage to discover deeper or more significant sequences of the infinite cause-and-effect chain in the researched area during the endless discovery of reality.** In discovering that endless cause-and-effect sequence, the most successful scientists can only grasp a deeper and more significant sequence than the one discovered so far, but they can never discover and comprehend **the infinity of cause-and-effect connections of phenomena, processes, and relationships in the world we live in.** This is because human science, with its limited senses and intellectual capacity, cannot, in an absolute sense, comprehend the complete causality of the most complex processes, phenomena, and relationships in certain researched segments of nature and society, taking into account the fact that nature and society are only a small but inextricably linked part of the endless universe.

In this sense, within the framework of rationalist epistemology, we can conclude that a theory can be brought down from the top only by another, better theory, based on the logical principles of argumentation and connected to indisputable and relevant facts from reality. **This implies that there is no absolutely best theory, but only a relatively best theory, which can be displaced from the scientific top by another relatively even better theory, and so on, in the endless discovery of reality, viewed according to human standards of ground truth.** If we were to claim the opposite – that science could fully discover the causes, for example, of crime – a sufficient scientific basis would be created for finding solutions to eradicate crime. At least for now, this is an impossible task. Given the above reasons, I believe that **reflective rationalist epistemology**, within which **critical empiricist positivism and realism** can be qualitatively developed, instead of the traditions of naïve positivist empiricism and naïve realism, should represent the scientific paradigm capable of responding to the challenges of the endless human discovery of paradoxical reality. **In contrast to this paradigm are other non-rationalist epistemological directions related to ontological orientations opposite to objectivism** (Alan Brayman, 2008). Non-rationalist epistemological directions basically consider knowledge and truth to be indeterminate and disputable because they experience them as subjectively dimensioned constructions of reality. For these reasons, they deny the possibility of objective comparison of knowledge between social scientists who have researched the same or similar topics in the same period and in the same space.

In this chapter, I believe it is necessary to shed new light on the wave of the **“inductivist illusion,”** a widespread tendency worldwide, not only in the context of naïve positivist empiricism and naïve realism, but also within constructionist and postmodernist-oriented “qualitative” research, toward which sociometric methods and various qualitative techniques for collecting and analyzing empirical data are inclined. The main goal here is to demystify and dispel the inductivist illusion that only, or predominantly, through inductive methods – by examining public opinion and using the SPSS software package with mathematical and statistical data-processing techniques – scientifically relevant knowledge can be obtained. The increasingly prevalent belief that sociometric or statistical methods can significantly replace the individual author’s intellectual capacity for abstract perception and penetration into the core of complex deterministic webs of phenomena, processes, and relationships is a serious misconception.

No matter how unacceptable the cruelty of this fact may be, the truth is undeniable that only on the basis of individual authorial intellectual ability – grounded in logical methods and combined with empirical methods based on previously indisputably proven facts, as well as relevant empirical data obtained not only through **quantitative methods** but also through **truly qualitative research methods such as observation, empirically confirmed *in vivo* cases, in-depth semi-structured interviews, and the like** – can revealing insights be achieved for explaining causal relationships, conducting deeper qualitative analyses of factor intercorrelations, and finding solutions for improving or overcoming negative situations in areas that are the subject of specific scientific research.

Accordingly, the criterion for testing hypotheses – especially in the domain of the revealing and explanatory functions of science aimed at discovering and explaining causes, scientific regularities, and complex deterministic networks – can only be indisputably proven and relevant empirical facts. Such a criterion cannot be forced public opinion research.

This position directly contradicts prevailing global tendencies in the social sciences, where dogmatically unified research patterns are instrumentalized to serve long-term geo-strategic and geo-economic interests of global capital, namely the realization of extraterritorial imperialist neo-colonialism, imposed through systemically corrupt foreign policies and the proclaimed neoliberal doctrine. The connection between imposed research patterns and these goals lies in the fact that science represents a subtle paradigm through which harmonization, approximation, and even unification of economic, political, legal, and especially educational systems can be achieved. Through imposed research models, the avant-garde scientific edge capable of transcending ideological boundaries and fostering awareness of the need for qualitative change is dulled and defocused (Miodrag Labović, 2024).

From the above statements, one should not conclude that **research on the public opinion of citizens** is scientifically useless or unnecessary. On the contrary, such research is necessary and has its own meaning and goals. However, those goals have a precisely defined purpose, which is completely different from the one stated above. Research on public opinion can contribute to the measurement of certain visible social phenomena. The necessity of such research is reflected in the fact that it provides relevant data on citizens' perception, alongside complementary statistical data on the conditions in a particular area of society. Additionally, this research can indicate areas that require more attention in the future through various forms of citizen education, improving their knowledge of certain phenomena in all their dimensions, forms and types. At the same time, research on public opinion aims to raise awareness of the seriousness of the risks and threats posed by certain phenomenon and to encourage active participation in addressing them. However, **public opinion research cannot substitute for the intellectual ability of scientists to discover the deepest causes of the most complex social phenomena, which are insufficiently known even to scientists themselves, or to find solutions to the most complex and abstract social problems, which are multifaceted, have accumulated over decades and therefore cannot be solved quickly.**

For these reasons, in the modern globalized world, as never before, **science has been instrumentalized and commercialized** to an unprecedented extent, among other things especially through the imposed tendency to publish **papers with the so-called "impact factor" in prestigious international scientific journals**. I am not competent to speak about the natural, mathematical and technical-technological sciences, so this statement applies to the social sciences, which, due to the nature of their subject of research cannot be completely de-ideologized. **Otherwise, the tendency to publish papers in the most prestigious scientific journals would not be at all controversial in itself if such journals evaluated immanent scientific functions and goals and distinguished between a truly original scientific paper, a scientific review (scientific-professional) paper, and a professional paper.** Of course, it is undeniable that papers published in such journals are of high professional quality. The filters in those journals are so rigorous that the papers published there are **high-quality professional papers or high-quality scientific review papers**. However, such papers very rarely, or almost never, possess the true scientific value associated with the most immanent scientific functions and goals, such as: **scientific discovery, scientific explanation, scientific forecast, scientific prediction of system-strategic approaches for designing long-term system-stable solutions**. These immanent scientific functions and goals are today almost not valued, unlike **professional functions and goals, such as description (which remains on the surface, at the external manifest level of phenomena, without delving into the deepest**

cause-and-effect connections of phenomena, processes and relationships), theoretical criticism, theoretical-interpretative and overview function, as well as certain practically applied works aimed at better practical application of the scientific-theoretical concepts from which international legal regulation and national legislation arise (Miodrag Labović, 2024).

In addition to the above, leading international scientific journals place strong emphasis on **impeccably executed technical standards** (compliance with margins, font type, headings, subheadings, etc.), as well as on **flawless English language usage**. In fact, there is often an explicit insistence on native-level English, which entails additional costs for engaging expensive professional translators who, beyond native proficiency, must also possess impeccable command of specialized academic terminology in English. **An additional financial burden arises from the acquisition of foreign scholarly literature**, given that small and economically less developed countries have very limited online access to relevant international scientific literature databases (e-journals and e-books) compared to highly developed countries, which invest incomparably greater financial resources in subscriptions to these electronic databases. Indicative in this regard is the fact that in North Macedonia only 0.3% of GDP is allocated to scientific research activities. This is four times lower than the European average and ten times lower than in highly developed EU countries.

Also, the financial condition of a particular author plays an important role – namely, how much the author is willing to pay for the work to be “open access.” Among other things, there is an **insistence on impeccably executed citation styles** (since, literally for a missed period or comma in the literature citation, most often the work of an insufficiently popular author is eliminated from the “competition” and is not published, without prior notification to the author).

The imposed methodological paradigms of naïve empiricist positivism (which we discussed above) are not officially stated as a requirement, but are unconditionally preferred. In truth, there are a small number of prestigious international scientific journals with a limited thematic scope where these methodological patterns are not considered a priority preference. In addition to the above, most often **an extremely limiting factor is the limited number of words for a paper, which in itself is unscientific, since it is contrary to the immanent scientific functions and goals, which do not recognize any limitations or the cutting of scientific truths into pieces.**

This is contrary to the systemic scientific approach, in the context of systems theory, which, among other characteristics, advocates the interconnection (coherence and complementarity) between multiple scientific fields, with the aim of a holistic, multidimensional and multidisciplinary, in-depth understanding of the entirety of a certain complex social problem, as opposed to partial, isolated and superficial understandings, in the context of the inductive illusion of data quantophobia.

(<https://www.mkd.mk/kolumni/kvantofrenijata-za-impakt-faktorot-preku-induktivistichkata-iluzija-na-brojkite>).

The intention of such logic is as follows: the more fragmented papers an author has, the more index points he can win. In such conditions, it is quite expected that there will be nothing or very little of real science, because real science recognizes limits only to stupidity (as a cosmic category) and nothing else (Miodrag Labović, 2024).

It is not at all a coincidence that the publishing networks of the most prestigious international scientific journals are called **“citation mafias”** (<https://www.enago.com/academy/citation-cartels-the-mafia-of-scientific-publishing/>).

Namely, through the officially unimposed but subtly preferred tendency to cite mostly authors who have published papers in the top 10% best-ranked journals, for example in the Scopus database (a network of scientific journals indexed in the Social Science Citation Index), these networks constantly increase their own ratings and the ratings of the most esteemed global authors. Related to this, *Webometrics*, one of the most famous rankings in the world that measures **university ratings, values exclusively the “scientific” component of papers published in the top 10% best-ranked journals in the aforementioned Scopus database** (<https://www.webometrics.info/en/Europe/North%20Macedonia>).

Consequently, if a scientist does not publish a paper and is not cited in those journals, it is considered the same as if he had not published anything anywhere. However, an objective scientific review by impartial and competent scientists could confirm a qualitative difference in the scientific value of an “ordinary” scientific paper compared to papers with the so-called “impact factor.”

In this way, professors-“scientists,” competing for the highest possible citation rating, contribute to increasing the ratings of global scientific journals and global authors, whose ratings are constantly growing, further sinking and “cementing” the publishing capacities of international scientific journals in underdeveloped and fragile societies at the bottom. An additional contribution to this negative tendency is made by the educational authorities in underdeveloped and immature societies, which, following world trends, cannot resist the trend of global “scientific competition,” nor penetrate the essence and background of this tendency. They legally oblige universities (and the units within them), as well as individual university professors, in various ways to unconditionally adhere to the conditions of the aforementioned tendency. After all, the main criterion for election to a higher teaching-scientific title, election to a national council for science, any other scientific board or commission for science, and even to the National Academy of Sciences and Arts, is the number of citations and the number of published papers in the most prestigious international scientific journals.

Otherwise, for the sake of truth, it must be said that publishing houses in underdeveloped countries are in such an unenviable situation, among other things, because of unprincipled collegial solidarity based on clientelist reviewers and authors of the majority of low-quality papers. However, it is an empirically confirmed fact that in international scientific journals of some underdeveloped countries, as well as in the proceedings of organized international scientific conferences, some of the papers with the qualification “original scientific paper” not only deserve this qualification, but also surpass in quality and scientific value similar papers published in highly prestigious international scientific journals.

As for the issue of the **democratization of science**, that is, the possibility for all experts to “vote” by citing certain papers and thereby determine the scientific value of those papers, I will state the following. As elitist as it may sound, it is an undeniable historical truth that science has never functioned, nor will it function, under the paradox of democracy understood one-dimensionally through its immanent principle of majority decision-making (Labović, 2020). According to the founder of social psychology, **Erich Fromm, if science were based on the majority representative-democratic principle of decision-making – that is, if the value of an idea were measured by the number of votes from voters (even if these were also university professors, who, for the sake of truth, are not all scientists) – humanity would remain at the level of cave civilization** (Erich Fromm, 1984).

This is because it is an undeniable truth that almost all epochal discoveries were the work of individuals and were later shared with close collaborators (today popularly called teams). Once they are accepted by a wider circle of scientists in the field of natural sciences, the discoveries are taken over by the real economy for mass industrial production used by the broad masses of people. The same occurs in the field of social sciences; only here, ultimately, the solutions must be accepted by governments in order to begin being used to achieve generally beneficial social goals.

It is a notorious historical fact that the greatest scientific discoveries and insights in the history of humankind were not accepted by their contemporaries and the highest scientific authorities of the time. **The most creative, revolutionary and avant-garde scientific ideas in the history of scientific thought were most often not accepted by the intellectual, political and business establishments at the time of their emergence, because they did not coincide with – and in fact destroyed – existing norms, standards, values and interests.** Some scientists paid with their lives for their scientific discoveries, such as **Galileo Galilei, Nicolaus Copernicus and Giordano Bruno**, while others died in severe material poverty, with their scientific insights being recognized and implemented only long after their death. Hence, creative and **revolutionary scientific ideas** with true scientific value are **timeless and supraspatial**, which is to say, **immortal**. Within historical frameworks, they are realized or gain value at a suitable socio-historical moment, in a given constellation of social forces and relations, when social conditions mature.

CONCLUSIONS

Under conditions of intensified **commercialization and instrumentalization of science** in the service of long-term geostrategic and geoeconomic interests of global centers of power (referring exclusively to works in the social sciences, given that they cannot be fully de-ideologized), it follows that differing value-based interpretations of undisputed facts constitute a significant potential risk as a “stumbling block.” It is a fact that today virtually anyone can publish scientific papers in international journals with a so-called “impact factor,” provided they are sufficiently persistent and willing to pay. In the interest of accuracy, publishing in international journals with a so-called “impact factor” does indeed function as a filter for high-quality professional papers, less frequently for scientific review (scholarly-professional) articles, and very rarely for original scientific works with genuine scientific value.

It is also a fact that most of the most prestigious international scientific journals insist on **naïve empiricist positivism and the inductivist illusion of numbers**, in the sense that objective scientific truth can be attained exclusively or predominantly through statistical and sociometric methods. Consequently, I argue that the **quantophrenia which imposes and demands exclusive publication in journals with an “impact factor,” rather than the pursuit of scientific works that may have a genuine impact on society, represents two fundamentally different things.**

For these reasons, I believe that greater value should be accorded to the immanent scientific functions and objectives discussed above, rather than focusing solely on the quantity of published papers with an impact factor (IF) and the number of citations – which, incidentally, at least in the social sciences, depends only minimally on the intrinsic scientific quality of a given work. Instead, citation counts are influenced to a much greater extent by, inter alia, where and in which journal an author has published, and whether a

particular author has been previously promoted and popularized. Most often, the most popular authors originate from major powers – countries in which the most prestigious global scientific journals are based. These authors are frequently chief editors, directors, or among the most commonly invited contributors to publish in such journals, where precisely their works receive the highest number of citations due to prestige, even when they are subject to negative criticism. By contrast, the unpopular author who has not published in prestigious scientific journals is not only rarely cited in a positive sense, but is typically not cited even in the context of negative critique.

Today, in the spirit of pragmatism and utilitarianism, the ability to “network” within various schemes – project consortia, international program boards, editorial boards, national councils, and similar bodies – has unfortunately become far more important than intellectual capacity for abstract perception and the attainment of cutting-edge scientific knowledge, the discovery of objective regularities, the penetration of deeper and more significant causal relationships among researched phenomena, processes and relations, or the design of new scientific-theoretical concepts or scientific theories as the result of long-term and painstaking research.

In this sense, I believe that the fulfillment of immanent scientific functions and goals – such as scientific discovery, scientific explanation, scientific prediction of practically applicable and realistically sustainable long-term, systemically stable solutions – should be valued far more highly than the number of citations, the h-index, or the sheer quantity of papers published in international journals with a so-called “impact factor.”

The lack of citations does not imply a lack of quality.

A large number of citations does not inevitably indicate high quality, but it also does not imply poor quality.

The scientific value of an article should depend on the fulfillment of the most immanent scientific functions and goals, such as scientific discovery, scientific explanation, scientific prognosis, and a systemically strategic projection of long-term, systemically stable solutions, in addition to expert functions such as description, theoretical critique, theoretically interpretive functions, and practical applicability.

These immanent scientific criteria gain particular importance in the contemporary digital era of AI, given the existence of numerous websites that offer finished articles prepared for the most prestigious international scientific journals with high “impact factor” values indexed in the Scopus or Web of Science databases.

The scientific quality of an article should be evaluated within an international open competition (a publicly announced scientific award or tender) by an Advisory Assessment Board composed of the most competent, impartial and independent scientists from all continents, within the relevant field. Any potential conflict of interest or commercial influence should be excluded.

A supervisory High-Level Committee is necessary in cases where a scientist believes that objective and precise criteria have not been respected and where there is no structural explanation in the decision regarding the ranking of individual applicants in the international open competition.

The number of citations and the number of papers published in the most prestigious international scientific journals cannot be the main criterion for promotion to higher teaching-scientific titles, selection to national science councils, other scientific boards or commissions, or membership in National Academies of Sciences and Arts.

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